

Fostering Improved Training Tools For Responsible Research and Innovation FIT4RRI

Experiment 3 Report *Material Science* (Deliverable 3.2)

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Definitions & Acronym

BSC: Balanced Scorecard

OS: Open Science

TOC: Theory of Change

R&I: Research and Innovation

RRI: Responsible Research and Innovation

Executive summary

The experiment wanted to demonstrate that RFPOs could offer an innovative range of public services, often business-based, capable of enhancing competitiveness and social value of their reference territories.

As a result, Saperi&Co. structure and objectives make it suitable for the establishment of a responsible governance. Hence, the underlying idea for putting into practice FIT4RRI Sapienza co-creation experiment is to implement at Saperi&Co. the first RRI-ruled Sapienza research centre, thus addressing the RRI key of governance, establishing at the same time, through the keys of science education and public engagement, a new dialogue with stakeholders on sustainability and bio-materials engineering, based on inclusiveness, idea co-generation and awareness.

1. Experiment description

The experiment has started to be planned in January 2018, based on, and in continuity with, the work carried on in Saperi&Co. project, with the main attempt of demonstrating a mutually advantageous effect deriving from the intersection of RRI and hard sciences environments.

It worked on the establishment of a RRI-ruled research center in Sapienza, capable of implementing – together with a responsible governance – public engagement and science education activities based on sustainability and bio-materials and deriving from hard sciences research.

More in detail, Saperi&Co. (Sapienza enhances research, innovation & co-working) is a project funded by structural funds aimed at implementing a distributed infrastructure based on interdisciplinarity, multi-actor approach and the sharing of competences and knowledge.

Saperi&Co. has been developed according to a hub-model putting together several laboratories and a central physical R&I infrastructure hosting:

- a fab-lab
- a coworking spaces
- a training room
- 4 lab based on regional S3.

Saperi&Co. offers a wide range of R&I services and, after the conclusion of the project on April the 30th, the University has established an interdepartmental research centre, including activities on sustainability and bio-materials engineering deriving from the Uniroma1 FIT4RRI group.

The main assumption of the experiment is to consider RRI as a governance dimension, to be combined with the more traditional ones (efficacy, efficiency and cost-effectiveness), to foster institutional change processes that, both in their design and assessment phases, should be driven by social responsibility too. This implies that a socially responsible approach to governance needs to be integrated with the economic/managerial one, to obtain a valuable and integrated (whole) governance model, according to a relationship of mutual dependence.

1.1 Organizer

Sapienza co-creation experiment is carried on by the Research Area of the University in team with the Department of Chemical, Material and Environmental Engineering. The experiment takes place in a recently established research and services centre, named Saperi&Co., whose management has been as well involved in the implementation of the experiment.

1.2 Aim & objectives

Sapienza co-creation experiment aim was to implement, within an ongoing Sapienza project aimed at the creation of a new research center, a responsible governance capable of strengthening the university's capacity of generating social impact and value. Among the envisaged values to be conveyed by the experiment there was sustainability.

The experiment's objectives can therefore summarised as follows:

- to test in a pilot scale the setting up of a multi-actor, co-created responsible governance in a complex environment trying to understand its limits and opportunities for a big organization such as Sapienza;
- to involve different stakeholders (e.g. scientists, companies, civil society, policy makers) in an open debate about sustainability, circular economy and bio-materials with the attempt of shaping a common scientific agenda;
- to engage families and especially school children, letting them experiencing, through hands on experiment, the role of sustainability in their daily life.

1.3 Selected RRI pillars

The co-creation experiment deals with 3 RRI pillars:

1. Governance
2. Public Engagement
3. Science Education

2. Internal stakeholders description

The internal stakeholders involved are:

- staff from Sapienza Research and Technology Transfer Area (ASuRTT)
- researchers, post docs and phd students from Sapienza Department of Chemical, Material and Environmental Engineering
- staff from Saperi&Co.

Nonetheless, the University governance has been informed of the experiments' progresses.

3. External stakeholders description

As far as it concerns external stakeholders, a different approach has been followed for the governance pillar, aimed at defining how to rule a research centre responsibly, and for the science education and public engagement pillars, aimed at involving especially civil society in sustainability matters.

More in detail, for the first pillar it has been involved a multi-stakeholders group:

- Matteo Lilli, Sapienza phd student in material engineering
- Alessia Quitadamo, Sapienza phd student in material engineering
- Andrea Sonnino, ENEA research centre
- Lorenzo Giorgi, President of Liter of Light NGO
- Davide Astiaso Garcia, General Secretary of ANEV (National Agency for Wind Energy)
- Chiara Petrioli, founder of W-Sewnse start up
- Michele Ortolani, Italian Institute of Technology
- Sesto Viticoli, Vice President of Italian Association for Industrial Reserach
- Fabrizio Rufo, Sapienza Professor in bioethics and citizen science
- Berenice Marisei, Lazio Innova (Region Lazio)

The group was coordinated by Andrea Riccio and Jacopo Tirillò.

On the other hand, the two other pillars have foreseen the involvement of about 15 families with children supported by Sapienza researchers.

4. First workshop outcome summary (September 2018)

The first workshop concerning the governance dimension of the experiment consisted in an ex ante analysis for designing the set up of Saperi&Co. as a RRI-ruled research centre and it was conducted by adopting a logic model as suggested by the Theory of Change (ToC)¹. This theory “defines long-term goals and then maps backward to identify changes that need to happen earlier (preconditions). The identified changes are mapped graphically in causal pathways of outcomes, showing each outcome in logical relationship to all the others. Interventions, which are activities and outputs of any sort, are mapped to the outcomes pathway to show what stakeholders think it will take to effect the changes, and when. Theory of Change provides a working model against which to test hypotheses and assumptions about what actions will best bring about the intended outcomes. A given Theory of Change also identifies measurable indicators of success as a roadmap to monitoring and evaluation.”²

The graphical representation of the framework could be presented as follows:

¹ The main reference is Weiss C. H., Exploring theory-based evaluation for comprehensive community initiatives for children and families, Aspen Insitute, New York, 1995

² Taplin D., Clark H., Collins E., Colby D.L., Theory of Change Technical Papers: A Series of Papers to support Development of Theories of change Based on Practice in the Field. ActKnowledge, New York, 2013, p.

Fig. 1 – A typical logic framework model (source: Carol Weiss)

To this regard:

- Inputs: all the economic and human resources employed by an organisation for developing a specific programme;
- Activities: the concrete actions deployed by an organisation to get outcomes and outputs and to pursue the organisation objectives;
- Outputs: the tangible products and services deriving from the organisation’s activities;
- Outcomes: the degree of change, the benefits and all the mid and long term effects deriving from the activities implemented within the organisation’s programme;
- Impact: the identification of wide and long-term outcomes directly deriving from the implemented actions.

The participatory design phase of the responsible governance of Saperi&Co. attended by the expert stakeholders listed in section 3 produced the following results:

Fig. 2 – Sapienza Experiment logic framework

The participatory design phase stressed some relevant aspects that can lead to the establishment of responsible governance in RFPOs. Among these:

- responsibility should be seen as a governance dimension, to be considered in organisations' management together with the most traditional one such as efficiency, efficacy and cost-effectiveness;
- the set up of responsible governance in RFPOs needs that scientific matters are informed by RRI (e.g. research integrity, gender balance, open science and access);
- responsible governance in RFPOs is *by definition* open to society and to external stakeholders to receive their feedbacks and contributions;
- responsible governance in RFPOs needs the establishment of common language, platforms and procedures to link the internal community, and then to develop fruitful science&society relations;
- among the main results of responsible governance in RFPOs should be included: real institutional change and the bridging of profit and no-profit R&I actions;
- responsible governance should be based on a shared set of values, reflected in simple but effective guidelines with proper indicators aimed at stressing the social value of R&I.

5. Second workshop outcome summary (April 2019)

The second expert stakeholders' workshop was focused, after the initial design phase of the responsible governance, on formalising in more detail its concrete implementation.

To cope with this goal, a Balanced Scorecard (BSC) Framework³ was used as a reference model in order to define and measure the strategy to be implemented according to four dimensions, each of them guided by a specific objective (see fig. 3):

- financial
- users perspective
- internal processes
- growth and innovation.

Fig. 3 – Sapienza experiment BSC

During the workshop, each of the four dimensions has been analysed in terms of objectives, related indicators and target, as well as possible actions. The following tables show the main outputs of the workshop that will lead – hopefully by the end of 2019 – to the definition of a set of guidelines for Saperi&Co. responsible governance.

1. Financial Perspective

³ The main reference is Kaplan R.S., Norton D.P., The Balanced Scorecard: Measures that Drive Performance, Harvard Business Review, 1992

TO INVEST ON RESPONSIBLE AND SUSTAINABLE ACTIONS

Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Develop a fundraising strategy for RRI and sustainability	N. of applications	3 applications per year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of funding opportunities • Mapping of potential sponsors • Develop a fundraising strategy • Apply for funding & sponsorships
	N. of requests for sponsorship	5 requests per year	
	% of successful initiatives	At least 1 initiative funded	

TO INVEST ON RESPONSIBLE AND SUSTAINABLE ACTIONS

Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Realize new investments on responsible and sustainable actions	% of expenditure for awareness campaign + events	5% total yearly budget	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop an awareness campaign on RRI • Organise events on responsibility and sustainability • Launch an internal call for ideas • Develop sustainable initiatives (e.g. plastic free)
	Call for ideas	Y/N budget allocated	
	% of expenditure for sustainability	5% total yearly budget	

2. Users perspective

TO ENGAGE USERS AND ENSURE THEIR SATISFACTION			
Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Engage users according to a quadruple helix perspective	Loyalty card + incentives	Y/N	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an engagement strategy for different stakeholders
	N. of request of info and subscriptions received	100 request per year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a loyalty card
	N. of interactions on social media	500 interactions per year	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop an incentives' structure

TO ENGAGE USERS AND ENSURE THEIR SATISFACTION			
Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Assess users' satisfaction (divided per target)	Decree of users' satisfaction measured through a questionnaire with score from 1 to 5	At least 60% of questionnaires scoring 4 or more	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a questionnaire, divided per target, to assess users' satisfaction
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Submit the questionnaires

3. Internal processes perspective

TO FOSTER THE UPTAKE OF A RESPONSIBLE GOVERNANCE			
Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Develop guidelines for responsible governance	% of leading figures involved in the design of the governance model	At least 50%	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement a participated consultation for writing the guidelines • Point out the main field of interest • Develop the guidelines
	N. of stakeholders involved in the process	100 stakeholders	
	Decree of engagement of quadruple helix stakeholders	At least 20%	
	Availability of guidelines	Y/N	

4. Growth & Innovation perspective

TO DEVELOP NEW INITIATIVES FOR RESPONSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY			
Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Co-create Saperi&Co. agenda with its stakeholders fostering inclusive R&I	N. of internal stakeholders involved	At least 50	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch a co-creation call to action for Saperi&Co. agenda • Develop a participatory tool • Organise bottom-up initiatives on responsibility and sustainability
	N. and type of external stakeholders involved	At least 20 from 5 different organisations	
	Participatory tool on the website	Y/N	
	N. of bottom-up initiatives launched	At least 3 per year	

TO DEVELOP NEW INITIATIVES FOR RESPONSIBILITY AND SUSTAINABILITY			
Objectives	Indicators	Target	Actions
Promote education and engagement activities focused on responsibility and sustainability on the territory	N. of citizens involved	150	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matchmaking between Saperi&Co. planning and SDGs
	N. of actions implemented	At least 5 actions	
	Decree of adherence to SDGs through a self-evaluation tool	30% of SDGs matched after year 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a self-evaluation tool for SDGs compliance • Development of education and engagement activities on responsibility and sustainability
	N. of partnerships activated	At least 10	

6. Awareness and engagement activities (May 2019)

Concerning Science Education and Public Engagement, training and awareness activities have been developed during May 2019 in tight collaboration with Sapienza Museums' Network.

These activities included, in particular, two hands on workshops for kids and their families respectively hold on May 18th and May 25th at Saperi&Co. and dedicated to:

- bioplastics' preparation with daily ingredients (e.g. coconut flour, organic waste...);
- super heroes 3D printing with organic materials.

The workshops were conducted by Sapienza researchers and addressed the role and relevance of sustainability and sustainable choices.

Engaging researchers in such activities of science education and public engagement represents a responsible action itself that shows how governance aspects are connected to all RRI pillars.

The workshops received a good degree of participation and an excellent level of satisfaction, with about 10-15 families joining each of the hands on session.

The brochure and some pictures concerning these initiatives are shown below:

 SAPERi&Co
Sapienza Enhances Research
Innovation and Coworking

in collaborazione con

Apertura Straordinaria
MAGGIO
MUSEALE

SAPERi&Co
Sapienza Enhances Research
Innovation and Coworking

7. Lessons learnt

7.1 Main blockers of quadruple helix co-creation

Sapienza experiment didn't encounter specific problem in working according to a quadruple helix co-creation approach. In fact, the design of the responsible governance action saw the participation of stakeholders from academia, enterprises, civil society and policy organisations while the awareness and education action established a good science&society relation.

Nonetheless, such cooperation among stakeholders was surely favored by the experiment venue, as Saperi&co. was funded by regional funds to be an interdisciplinary and multi-actors hub highly devoted to co-creation and cross-fertilization.

By the way, the workshops hold in Sapienza – apart from the experiment’s results – underlined a common difficulty in establishing starting from academia a quadruple helix approach to co-creation. The Italian university system, indeed, is still reluctant to cross-fertilization and doesn’t have a proper national strategy and/or incentives structure to favor it.

7.2 Proposed consensus strategies & co-creation approaches/frameworks

The strategies and approaches used to gain consensus and co-creation were described in previous sections in terms of tools and reference framework (e.g. Teory of Change, BSC).

For sure, all the activities were based on participatory approaches guided by a moderator that fostered the proper engagement of all participants and tried to reach consensus where the stakeholders didn’t agree on some aspects.

7.3 Most relevant RRI practices (from WP1 and WP2) for the experiment

More than practices deriving from WP1 and WP2, the experiment took inputs from the analysis proposed within the 2 WPs. More in detail, RRI trends and barriers produced in WP1 were taken into consideration in the design participatory phase and were part of the debate with stakeholders; similarly the thematic and national context analysis developed in WP2 was useful to define the role of academia on bio-materials and sustainability topic and define the engagement and education activities.

7.4 Institutional changes required to fully embed the chosen RRI pillars

RRI and OS in the Italian system could refer to the so-called university “third mission”, intended as the capability of academia of implementing trusted, mutual and socially fruitful science and society relations. Implementing third mission, especially at the governance level, as the experiment does, implies to move towards institutional change.

As a consequence, Sapienza co-creation experiment surely laid the groundwork for some degrees of institutional change, especially by informing the university governing bodies and involving researchers in responsible governance matters and actions, thus making them aware that responsibility and openness – far from being the latest administrative processes to comply with – could represent an added value in their research work. Some policies, as further described in the following paragraph, have already been put into practice benefiting from both the experiment itself and a systemic growing attention to university third mission.

7.5 Policy support/changes required to properly embed RRI in the ongoing research with the involvement of the quadruple helix

The final aim of the co-creation experiment will be to define a simple set of guidelines (about 10 main points) for responsible governance within Saperi&Co. To be effective, the guidelines should be approved by the university governing boards, thus witnessing a political support towards RRI and OS.

Nonetheless some policies to favor this process have already been launched:

- creation of a working group including both research and administrative staff to cope with definitions and indicators concerning third mission;

- launch of an internal call for funding (total budget 200 K euro) for implementing science and society relations.

7.6 Any issues/constraints noticed during the experiment implementation (i.e. procedural issues)

The experiment didn't encounter obstacles in its implementation up to now. Procedures were smooth and participation was high.

Nonetheless, to really institutionalise RRI within the university governance it will be necessary to face some barriers (see also what emerged from FIT4RRI deliverable 2.1):

- Political barriers, due to the lack of national legislation to support RRI;
- Institutional barriers, deriving from limited commitment of research institutions' managers towards RRI as well as the discontinuity of institutional mechanisms and structures that allow the incorporation of RRI into the organization;
- Social barriers, generated by the potential limited interest and lack of awareness of the stakeholders (local authorities, companies, civil society organizations, citizens) towards the RRI, as well as their lack of competences to understand scientific issues.

8. Next steps

As already mentioned, next main goal will be the set up and approval of guidelines for responsible governance within Saperi&Co. The guidelines will be assessed by the expert stakeholders' group that already worked in the participatory design phase.

Once the guidelines will be approved, they could represent a relevant base to scale up responsible governance to Sapienza and/or other university research centre.

Another future goal is to organize within Saperi&Co. engagement and science education activities on a more regular base, involving not only civil society but also the other quadruple helix actors.

Furthermore, there is the will to connect the experiment with other ongoing initiatives such as CIVIS project funded under the Erasmus European Universities call. In fact, CIVIS foresees that Sapienza will organize a set of open labs for involving and engaging stakeholders in research issues.

Appendix A – Experiment KPIs

DESCRIPTION		NOTES
RELEVANCE		
Scope of the experimentation		
R1 RRI pillars focused upon*	This is a quantitative indicator. It refers to the 5 RRI/OS pillars and the governance of RRI/OS.	3
R2 RRI best practices considered for assessment of their potential implementation in the ongoing research*	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to the best practices developed under the experiment's design phase which are considered (by the organisation or other relevant actors)	The participatory process for pointing out issues and indicators for responsible governance (through

	relevant and thus deserving to be implemented.	ToC and BSC) is for sure a best practice. Also the engagement and education activities will be further implemented.	
R3	Connection with existing policies/measures developed by the organisation	This is a qualitative indicator. The question is understanding to what extent the experiment is connected with and takes into consideration the existing policies at the organisation level . For example, if there is a budget heading the experiment could refer to, if there is a policy context where the experiment could be framed, etc.	The working group and the call for funding on third mission represent a connection with existing measures
<i>Mobilisation of internal actors</i>			
R7	Active involvement of the organisation's management *	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving the top management at the relevant level (e.g., department level, HR offices, University board, etc.). Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, meetings with the team, technical and organisational support, etc.)	The experiment was implemented by the research and TT area of Sapienza, that represent one of university management office. Furthermore, the governing bodies have always been informed
R8	Active involvement of researchers *	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving researchers. Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, support to the planned actions, etc.)	Researchers both from Saperi&Co. and of Department of Chemical, Material and Environmental Engineering jopined meetings regularly and were involved both in the design and implementation of the experiment. Researchers from other areas also joined the workshops.
<i>Mobilisation of external actors</i>			
R9	Active involvement of quadruple helix actors*	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at understanding to what extent the experiment succeeded in involving quadruple helix actors. Involvement can be assessed in different ways (participation in meetings and initiatives, support to the planned actions, etc.)	Quadruple helix actors were highly involved in all activities (especially workshops) concerning the governance pillar

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	NOTES	
EFFECTIVENESS			
<i>Implementation process</i>			
E1	Actual implementation of the planned actions	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment sticks to established plans. Deviations not necessarily refers to problems in the implementation process, but can also be an effort to make the experiment more effective or relevant to the context.	The experiment was implemented according to the plans. With more time available, even thje guidelines could have been defined
E2	Compliance with planned schedules and deadlines	This is a qualitative indicator, aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment sticks to established plans. Deviations not necessarily refers to problems with the implementation process, but can also be an effort to make the experiment more effective or relevant to the context.	See E1
<i>Beneficiaries</i>			
E4	Match between the type of intended beneficiaries and the type of the actual beneficiaries	This is a qualitative indicator, the significance of which may vary according to the experiment.	There was a good matching

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	NOTES	
IMPACT			
<i>Objective impact – Institutional agreement</i>			
I1	Number of quadruple helix consensus solutions (common agreed plans/steps) for supporting the embedment of RRI *	This is a quantitative indicator. It refers to the level of involvement of external players in the experiment through formal arrangements. This indicator could be also relevant for the dimension “Sustainability”	Sapienza has activated a formal agreement with AIRI
<i>Objective impact – Expected changes</i>			
I2	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes at the level of the research group/department/quadruple helix actors directly involved with the experiment	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to any significant change in the life of the organisation at the relevant organisational level directly due to the experiment. Any modification observed during and after the implementation phase deserves anyhow to be recorded.	Surely the engineering researchers involved in the experiment are much more aware of RRI and its benefits
I3	Actual introduction of organisational, regulatory or procedural changes in parts of the organisation not directly involved with the experiment	This is a qualitative indicator. It refers to indirect effects of the experiment on other parts of the organisation, which can be viewed as a precursor of an embedment process of RRI/OS.	The call for funding will be open to the entire Sapienza community
<i>Objective impact – Multiplicative effects</i>			
I6	Observation of result/best practice multiplication in the	This is a qualitative indicator. Differently from the previous one,	As already mentioned, there is a growing

quadruple helix ecosystem generated through the experiment *	which are mainly interested in new actions or reactions, this indicator should capture larger forms of mobilisation on RRI/OS occurred beyond the scope of the experiment.	attention in Sapienza towards responsibility and sustainability actions. These go beyond the experiment but have been partly influenced by it.
<i>Objective impact – Communication impacts</i>		
I7 Increased visibility of the experiment within the organisation	This indicator is of a qualitative nature and refers to the presence of information on the experiment or on RRI/OS related issues in, e.g., institutional websites, meetings, newsletters, internal communication channels, and the like. The more the experiment is known, the more is likely to have an impact on the organisation.	The engagement and education activities of the experiment have been well promoted on Sapienza website and newsletter as well as on social channels (e.g. twitter)
I8 Increased visibility of the experiment outside the organisation	This indicator is of a qualitative nature and refers to the presence of information on the experiment or on RRI/OS-related issues because of the experiment outside the organisation.	See I8
<i>Subjective impact – Changes in the perception of RRI/OS</i>		
I14 Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	This is a qualitative indicator. It should measure to what extent the experiment raised a greater interest towards RRI/OS, regardless to the orientation (positive or negative), in the internal actors. It is also possible to make the indicator quantitative using a 5-point scale. However, qualitative aspects should be also considered.	All these dimensions (I14 to I21) will be assessed once the guidelines will be developed through a dedicated survey
I15 Changes in the interest in RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	This is a qualitative indicator. It should measure to what extent the experiment raised a greater interest towards RRI/OS, regardless to the orientation (positive or negative), in the internal actors. It is also possible to make the indicator quantitative using a 5-point scale. However, qualitative aspects should be also considered.	
I16 Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Awareness refers here to the attitude of the actors to consider RRI/OS as an important aspect of the life of the organisation interviews are part of. Therefore, awareness refers to a positive orientation towards RRI/OS. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.	
I17 Changes in the awareness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Awareness refers here to the attitude of the actors to consider RRI/OS as an important aspect of the life of the organisation interviews are part of. Therefore, awareness refers to a positive orientation towards RRI/OS.	

	This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.
I18 Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of each internal actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Usefulness can be considered as a precursor of a future mobilisation in support to the implementation of RRI/OS. It refers to the recognition of the capacity of RRI/OS to address problems that the actors are already dealing with. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.
I19 Changes in the perceived usefulness of RRI/OS of quadruple helix actors (at the beginning & end of the experiment) *	Usefulness can be considered as a precursor of a future mobilisation in support to the implementation of RRI/OS. It refers to recognition of the capacity of RRI/OS to address problems that the actors are already dealing with. This indicator is qualitative in nature but a 5-point scale can be also used.
<i>Subjective impact – Orientation towards future involvement</i>	
I20 Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of each internal actors	This is a qualitative indicator which can be also expressed in quantitative ways through 5-point scales. Differently from usefulness, this indicator assess the personal involvement of the actors in RRI/OS
I21 Explicit orientation to promote/ get involved in future RRI/OS-oriented activities of quadruple helix actors	This is a qualitative indicator which can be also express in quantitative way through 5-point scales. Differently from usefulness, this indicator should measure the personal involvement of the actors in RRI/OS

CODE & INDICATOR	DESCRIPTION	NOTES
SUSTAINABILITY		
<i>Recommendations produced</i>		
S1 Policy change recommendations *	This indicator is aimed at measuring the capacity of the experiment to “launch” possible future RRI/OS-oriented policies at the relevant organisational level. This indicator is of a qualitative nature	The experiment for sure offers a solid base for future RRI oriented policies
S2 Organisational change recommendations *	This indicator is aimed at measuring the capacity of the experiment to “launch” possible future RRI/OS-oriented changes in organisational practices at the relevant organisational level. This indicator is of a qualitative nature	Similarly, the experiment has launched possible RRI oriented organizational practices
<i>Institutional links and agreements</i>		
S3 Creation of links with key players not previously engaged in the implementation of the experiment	This indicator is intended to assess the capacity of the experiment to activate new possibly permanent social configurations and cooperation relationships. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	

S4	Creation of stable links with other bodies involved in the implementation of the experiment	This indicator is intended to assess the capacity of the experiment to activate new possibly permanent social configurations and cooperation relationships. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	For sure the stakeholders involved in the experiment have expressed their wish to keep working more permanently on the theme. AIRI has already organized a technical table for RRI in industry using the experiment as a successful use case
S5	Industry/RFPO proposals for collaboration with researchers *	This indicator is intended to assess if the experiment led to the establishment of clear or possibly formal new cooperation programmes. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	New programmes seems possible
S6	Society-driven proposals for collaboration with researchers *	This indicator is intended to assess if the experiment led to the establishment of clear or possibly formal new cooperation programmes. This indicator is of a qualitative nature.	New programmes seems possible
<i>Institutionalisation processes within the organisation</i>			
S7	Identification/acquisition of new resources to continue the activities or parts of them	This is a qualitative indicator aimed at assessing to what extent the organisation or other internal and external actors are leaned to invest on RRI/OS in the future. This can be a composite set of indicators, also including quantitative indicators (e.g., quantity of resources, number of sources, etc.)	Among the resources there are for sure new call for proposal under H2020 but also cooperation with ongoing projects such as CIVIS or EuSRExcel
S8	Establishment of institutional arrangements to make the new operational setups activated by the actions definitive (e.g., institutionalisation of scholarships, drafting of internal regulations that establish procedures to access certain benefits, etc).	This is a qualitative indicator aimed at assessing to what extent the experiment already led to the establishment of new permanent solutions inspired to RRI/OS at the relevant organisational level (department, organisation, etc.).	There are no permanent solutions yet, but some pilot experimentations such as the call for funding